

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE SYSTEM OF INTERNATIONAL LEGAL INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROTECTION OF CHILDREN'S RIGHTS

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Abstract.

In this article, the general description of the system of international legal documents on children's rights and their protection is studied and discussed on the basis of scientific, theoretical and legal evidence.

Keywords: Child rights, child protection, international community, League of Nations, minor, classification, declaration, Child trafficking.

The well-being of children and their rights have always been the focus of the international community. The first documents on children's rights were adopted at the beginning of the 20th century, in 1919 by the International Labor Organization, Convention No. 5 on the Minimum Age for Employment in Industry, and in 1924 by the League of Nations, the Geneva Declaration of the Rights of the Child was adopted.¹ From this period, children's rights were mainly limited to taking measures against slavery, child labor, child trafficking and pornography of minors. , a large base of international legal documents reflecting all its rights and freedoms and special rights has been formed. Of course, these documents complement each other, and at the same time, they differ from each other, and it would be wrong to always treat them as the same. Therefore, when studying the nature of these documents, which are considered international agreements, and their specific features, it is appropriate to study these agreements by classifying them. Generally, it is accepted to classify international agreements based on the following criteria:

- from the point of view of the legal force of international documents: documents with an imperative character, whose general name is more commonly called "convention";
- special documents dedicated to certain areas of children's rights and general documents covering all areas of children's rights;
- on the issue of membership, universal international agreements aimed at covering all countries and regional documents covering certain countries of the region. ²

Documents that include universal norms on children's rights can also be classified as follows:

- General declarations and conventions of the UN, called universal standards of human rights: universal documents such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights;

¹ Jeneva deklaratsiyasi 1924-yil.

² Sh.R.Nuriddinov. Bolalar huquqlarini ximoya qilishning o'ziga xos usullari 2018

– Documents adopted by specialized organizations of the UN, such as UNESCO, ILO, in the fields of education and work;

– declarations and conventions aimed at special regulation of children's rights.

Regional international documents in the field of children's rights can also be classified as follows:

– Documents aimed at the cooperation of the countries of the European region;

– Documents aimed at the cooperation of the countries of the African region;

– Documents aimed at the cooperation of the countries of the American region.

When thinking about the regional documents on the protection of children's rights, it can be seen from the above picture that the existing documents are mainly related to the European, American and African continents. Unfortunately, such a document has not yet been developed for the Asian region, where ensuring children's rights is complicated and problematic. This is characterized by the absence of a regional mechanism for human rights in this region and the fact that interstate regional cooperation in this area is very weak.

The classification of international documents on children's rights shows that, firstly, it helps to correctly understand the content of international documents in the field of children's rights, and secondly, that the international legal framework in the field of children's rights is developing both universally and regionally, but, which shows the picture that the development is not the same in all regions. At the same time, it helps to understand that factors such as the differences in the political and economic structure of the states in different regions, their religious and cultural diversity are the factors affecting the regional integration of the states in this area. Thirdly, based on the classification of international agreements on children's rights, it facilitates the study of national legal documents and their norms in accordance with them. This is of great theoretical and practical importance in researching and studying the improvement of national legislation based on international norms. For example, when considering the implementation of the Convention on the Rights of the Child into national legislation, first of all, the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" or the ILO's documents on child labor should be considered. When thinking about the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and similar national legislative documents regulating labor relations are understood.

The development of international cooperation on children's rights has led to the formation of a system of protection of children's rights at the regional level. That is, in different regions of the world, specific models of protection of human rights, including children's rights, have emerged. Such models have shown their efficiency in many ways than the universal system. Such regional organizations include the European System for the Protection of Human Rights, the American System for the Protection of Human Rights, the African System for the Protection of Human Rights and Peoples' Rights, the Permanent Arab Commission on Human Rights, adopted within the framework of the CIS CIS Conventions on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of May 26, 1995 may be included.

The Economic and Social Council conducts its activities with the help of committees working during the sessions - Economic, Social and Coordinating Committees. Documents on issues of human rights, including children's rights, are prepared by the Social Committee. The reports of the social committee are approved at the plenary sessions of the Economic and Social Council.

In addition, the Economic and Social Council cooperates with specialized organizations that devote a significant part of their activities to issues related to human rights, in particular, the International Labor Organization, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and others on behalf of the UN. The Economic and Social Council generally coordinates work in this regard by conducting consultations and developing recommendations..

The Human Rights Commission conducted studies and research in the field of human rights, made recommendations aimed at further improving the work in this field and more effectively ensuring and protecting human rights and freedoms, and disseminated information. The Human Rights Council, which was established in its place, was given wider powers. It should be noted that the Human Rights Commission was established within the Economic and Social Council and has been fulfilling its tasks, while the Human Rights Council has been transformed into an auxiliary body of the General Assembly..³

In 1990, the UN Commission on Human Rights adopted resolution 1990/68, according to which it decided to appoint a Special Rapporteur on child trafficking, prostitution and pornography. The special rapporteur's mandate includes presenting a report to the UN General Assembly and the Human Rights Commission (now the Human Rights Council) on the investigation and results of the exploitation of children in the world and making recommendations aimed at protecting the rights of the child. These recommendations are also addressed to governments, UN agencies and non-governmental organizations.

Human Rights Council, Special Rapporteur since March 2011

Re-appointed for 3rd year. The special rapporteur was mandated to visit countries and communicate with governments on the following issues:

- Analysis of child trafficking, prostitution and pornography;
- Identifying new patterns of child trafficking, prostitution and pornography;
- Develop, adapt and share best practices to combat child trafficking, prostitution and pornography;
- Continue to develop effective strategies to combat child trafficking, prostitution and pornography;

It should also be noted that in accordance with the resolution of the General Assembly adopted on December 14, 1955, the Secretary-General has the authority to provide assistance in the protection of human rights at the request of governments in the following form:

- a) providing consulting services with the support of experts;
- b) conducting seminars;
- v) providing scholarships to encourage specialization in human rights issues.

The Committee on the Rights of the Child plays an important role in the UN system on the rights of the child as a treaty body of the UN on human rights. Detailed information about the legal status and activities of this body will be provided in the next chapter.

³ R.N.Omomnov Toshkent Huquqiy tartibot 2019

